

Retaining Complaining Customers: Understanding Equity–Trust Trade-Offs

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Even customers who invest substantial resources into a relationship with a firm might face a complaint episode and consider whether to switch to another provider. Raising a challenge to the conventional wisdom that suggests increasing relationship investments monotonically lower the risks of complaint-driven consumer churn, the current research identifies another pattern, in which such complaint-driven churn is greatest among customers who invest moderately in their relationships with the firm. The resulting “equity–trust retention curve” follows a U-shaped pattern. To explain it, the authors propose an equity–trust framework that depicts how complaints simultaneously undermine equity and trust, and relationship investments differentially moderate both mechanisms by amplifying equity-based losses but buffering trust erosion. Across both a game-theoretic model and controlled experiments, the findings validate the framework. In turn, applying this framework can enable firms to classify complainers as transactional, switching, or relational and better understand the drivers of their retention.

Keywords: complaint churn, customer investments, equity, trust, retention

Retaining customers who are dissatisfied enough to complain represents a persistent, as well as costly, challenge for firms. Despite decades of research, firms also remain uncertain about how to identify precisely which customers will leave after they voice their complaints (Homburg and Fürst 2005). For example, in rich research into service failures, recovery, and complaint handling, some studies recommend compensation and prompt redress to encourage customers to stay (McCollough, Berry, and Yadav 2000; Smith, Bolton, and Wagner 1999), but others argue that compensation is ineffective (Blodgett and Tax 1993). Meta-analytic reviews reinforce the inconsistent findings and theoretical fragmentation (Gelbrich and Roschk 2011). Consequently, both researchers and practitioners know a lot of tactics, but the mechanisms that actually prevent complaining customers (i.e., those who experience a complaint episode, consisting of a cause leading to dissatisfaction, such as a service or product underperformance, followed by a complaint action) from churning, and when, remain unclear.

A relationship perspective promises some insights into these questions (Palmatier 2008). It holds that customers' relationship investments, including the time, effort, spending, and other resources they devote to strengthening their firm relationships, represent deeply embedded resources allocated to the relationship. A customer who has accumulated substantial familiarity with a firm's processes or interfaces, established routines through repeated interactions, and developed an emotional connection with the brand as a default provider, seemingly should be less likely to leave. Yet customers' relationship investments do not guarantee their longer tenure, satisfaction, or loyalty. Rather, and in the specific case of complaining customers, we predict that their relationship investments exhibit a U-shaped relationship with retention likelihood, such that churn among complainers is greatest for those who have devoted a moderate level of investment to their relationship with the firm.

This reasoning relies on both relational and transactional exchange perspectives. A complaint episode tends to prompt customers to reassess the relationship, because the episode simultaneously undermines their expectation of an equitable distribution between what they have invested in the relationship and what they receive in return, as well as their trust in the firm. Notably, customers who make moderate relationship investments likely have developed expectations of an equitable relationship, but they might not have a strong sense of relationship trust. Such relationship investments also influence the impact of complaints on churn, because they shift the dominant evaluative lens from transactional and equity-driven, as is common in low-investment relationships, to relational and trust-driven, as tends to be more prominent in high-investment relationships. As customers' relationship investments increase, so do their equity expectations, such that their complaint implies a greater perceived equity loss. But greater investments also support stronger trust, which can buffer the negative effects of a complaint. These countervailing forces imply a U-shaped equity–trust retention curve, in which a failure that prompts a complaint drives customers who have moderate investments to leave, more so than low-investment complainers who have not established strong equity expectations, or high-investment complainers who trust the firm sufficiently to stay.

We test these predictions with a multimethod approach. The analytical approach in Study 1 leverages a game-theoretic model of two competing firms and their heterogeneously invested customers to establish formally that complaint costs and transition costs—analogueous to equity and trust perceptions—together generate a U-shaped retention pattern. This demonstration of how the proposed U-shaped effect emerges from underlying cost functions does not rely on either psychological assumptions or bounded rationality. With two experiments, Study 2 complements the analytical model by testing the proposed framework in a controlled scenario.

Through randomized manipulations of both complaint and investment levels, Study 1a focuses primarily on lower-investment, more *transactional relationships*, whereas Study 1b examines higher-investment, more *relational relationships*. Across the two experiments, we test both mechanisms and compare their relative magnitude and power in driving post-complaint retention. In this way, we confirm that the relative power of equity (trust) to drive retention gradually decreases (increases) as relationship investments increase. The two studies provide convergent evidence, indicating the internal and theoretical validity of our framework.

As a complement to this analytical and experimental evidence, we conduct a large-scale empirical analysis using proprietary, customer-level data from a global financial services firm, which we report in the Web Appendix. For thousands of banking customers, we assess retention after they complain. The empirical results verify the predicted U-shaped effect of complainers' relationship investments on post-complaint retention, such that complainers with a moderate number of accounts are least likely to stay, whereas those with more or less investments exhibit higher post-complaint retention. Thus, we find supporting evidence for the relevance of the equity–trust retention curve in a real-world, banking context.

On the basis of these findings, we offer three main contributions to extant literature. First, we identify a U-shaped relationship between complaining customers' relationship investments and their post-complaint retention, such that churn is highest among moderately invested customers. We define this segment of customers as existing in a potential “switching region,” a notion that is both theoretically and managerially consequential. In particular, it challenges a common assumption that increasing relationship investments provide more protection to firms. Instead, we establish that retention is lowest when customers have devoted enough investments

to heighten their equity expectations but not enough to stabilize relational trust, leaving them vulnerable to churn.

Second, we offer an equity–trust trade-off account of this U-shaped effect, which explicitly avoids a simplified equivalence in which equity arises in purely transactional exchanges or trust occurs only in purely relational exchanges. As we show, complaints simultaneously undermine perceptions of relationship equity and trust in the firm, and customers’ relationship investments moderate these pathways. They do so in opposing directions, such that investments amplify perceptions of equity violations by heightening their expectations, but they reduce the risk of eroded trust by providing accumulated relational assurance. In the experimental findings, we learn that when investments are low to medium (mainly transactional region), equity ($\beta = .52$) exerts a stronger influence on retention than trust does ($\beta = .15$). As investments increase to the medium to high level (mainly relational region), equity ($\beta = .30$) instead becomes less influential than trust ($\beta = .39$). This pattern is consistent with the idea that “relationships often require greater resource commitment and investment than transactional” interactions (Whipple, Lynch, and Nyaga 2010, p. 514). This equity–trust trade-off account offers a clearer view of how investments reshape the relative influence of equity- and trust-based evaluations following a complaint.

Third, we derive a framework for identifying which complainers are most at risk of churn, namely, those that appear in the switching region. Rather than an implicit “more investment = safer from churn” heuristic, this framework offers a more precise prediction: Moderately invested complainers experience strong equity concerns, without robust trust buffers, so they are the ones most likely to leave. Our experimental findings help specify that a one standard deviation increase in relationship investments, relative to the average level in the

switching region, increases retention by 3.7%. Given evidence that even relatively small increases in customer retention can generate disproportionately large downstream gains in customer lifetime value and profitability—with some estimates suggesting that a 5% increase in retention may raise profits by 25%–95%, depending on the industry context—this effect is economically meaningful. Therefore, firms can use this framework to assign complaining customers to specific regions, whether more transactional, switching, or more relational, and accordingly predict which recovery levers are more or less likely to succeed (e.g., restore equity with compensation or focus on trust repair).

Literature Review

In developing the conceptual framework for this research, as detailed in the next section, we turn to marketing research pertaining to complaint management and customer retention strategies (for reviews, see Kumar and Kaur 2020; Orsingher, Valentini, and De Angelis 2010; Stone 2011), different types of exchanges, equity, trust, and relationship investments.

Complaint and Retention

Building on the exit–voice–loyalty–neglect framework (Farrell 1983; Hirschman 1972), prior research conceptualizes complaining as a voice response to some issue, which customers use in an attempt to remedy their dissatisfaction (Fornell and Wernerfelt 1987). Firms in turn must engage in systematic complaint management, including receiving, investigating, resolving, and preventing failures and customer dissatisfaction, to achieve customer recovery (Hansen, Wilke, and Zaichkowsky 2010). Prior research details various antecedents of complaining behavior (e.g., prior experience, situational factors, dissatisfaction), relevant drivers of

complaint-related churn (e.g., trust, satisfaction, perceived equity, prior complaints, purchases), and effective recovery tactics (e.g., prompt response, compensation, courtesy) (e.g., Ahn, Han, and Lee 2006; Borah, Prakhya, and Sharma 2020; Davidow 2003; Knox and Van Oest 2014; Singh and Wilkes 1996). Yet even with these pertinent insights, some variations remain unexplained. For example, identical complaint handling tactics can succeed for some customers but fail for others, suggesting the need for further research into why churn after complaints varies.

Transactional–Relational Exchange Continuum

A broad shift in marketing thought, reflecting the reality of marketing interactions, moves away from regarding market exchanges “as transactions that need to be consummated” and toward conceiving of them “as relationships that need to be nurtured, preserved, and cultivated” (Agustin and Singh 2005, p. 96). Whereas transactional exchanges emphasize short-term, cost–benefit considerations and fairness, relational exchanges prioritize trust, interdependence, and long-term mutual commitment (Hingley et al. 2011; Sheth and Shah 2003; Whipple, Lynch, and Nyaga 2010). Customer–firm relationships can vary along this continuum, though the implications of such exchange styles for customers’ evaluations following a negative event have not been fully established (Fruchter and Sigué 2005). For example, customers at intermediate points along the transactional–relational continuum might exhibit systematically different responses and behaviors than customers who engage in mainly transactional or mainly relational exchanges, especially when facing a complaint episode.

Equity and Trust

According to equity theory, people evaluate exchanges by comparing their inputs with their outcomes, and if the exchange appears inequitable, they experience dissatisfaction and seek

to restore its fairness (Adams 1965). Such perceptions also influence customers' satisfaction, evaluations, and emotions (e.g., Tax, Brown, and Chandrashekar 1998). In addition, trust has been defined in many ways. Andaleeb (1996, p. 79) describes it as "the willingness of a party to rely on the behaviors of others, ... preceded by the focal party's belief that the partner's actions will lead to favorable outcomes." Customer trust in turn can positively influence customer loyalty (e.g., Gounaris 2005; Ranaweera and Prabhu 2003; Reichheld and Schefter 2000). Both equity and trust notions have appeared in studies of complaint management too, though gaps remain. Orsingher, Valentini, and De Angelis (2010, p. 184) pose a long list of open questions regarding complaint handling and customers' satisfaction. Questions also remain regarding the extent to which trust drives relevant consumer outcomes, such as loyalty (Yim, Tse, and Chan 2008). In line with calls for further research, we extend the theorizing to consider how both equity and trust perceptions might shift following an event that prompts a complaint, with potentially contrasting influences on customer churn. We also predict that their relative dominance might vary with the extent of customer investment in the relationship, as we address next.

Switching Costs and Investments

Customer relationship investments and switching costs are closely linked. As Burnham, Frels, and Mahajan (2003, p. 119) note, when "customers use more types of a providers' products, they appear to enter a more advanced relationship stage in which switching is more costly." In this sense, customer investments, together with other factors, like perceptions of product and market characteristics or domain expertise, function as antecedents of switching costs (Burnham, Frels, and Mahajan 2003). Although an in-depth analysis of the links between relationship investments and switching costs is beyond the scope of the current research, we

postulate that switching costs can be inferred from customers' relationship investments. Thus, higher investments typically increase switching costs, and these costs have critical influences on customer retention (e.g., Ahn, Han, and Lee 2006; Li 2015). The exact effects of switching costs are uncertain though, because studies indicate both positive (Choi 2020; Shi 2013) and negative (Cabral 2009, 2016; Dubé, Hitsch, and Rossi 2009) effects on retention. According to Edward, George, and Sarkar (2010), some of these inconsistencies might arise because various studies account for the influences of switching costs using different measures. Such evidence indicates a gap, due to the absence of an integrative explanation of the outcomes of switching costs. We seek to address this gap by proposing that they might exert nonmonotonic effects on customer retention following a complaint. However, our theoretical framework locates this nonmonotonicity in customers' equity and trust perceptions rather than in the mechanical cost of switching per se.

Conceptual Framework

On the basis of the preceding literature review, we predict that complaints affect customer retention outcomes through both equity and trust, as evaluative mechanisms. We also anticipate that these effects might vary with customers' relationship investments. Therefore, we propose a conceptual framework of the U-shaped relationship between investments and post-complaint retention, in which we seek to uncover and clarify the mechanisms that drive this pattern. In so doing, we distinguish carefully between the conceptual constructs we propose and their empirical operationalizations. For the purposes of the current research, relationship investments, equity perceptions, and trust perceptions constitute theoretical constructs that

capture underlying transactional and relational states. Relationship investments reflect the accumulated commitments and resources that customers have devoted to their relationship with the firm. Equity and trust perceptions represent evaluative mechanisms that customers leverage when facing a complaint episode and deciding to remain with or switch from the firm. For our subsequent studies, we operationalize these constructs with contextual proxies (e.g., accounts, perceived unfairness, perceived trustworthiness).

Independent Variable: Customer Complaints

Following a negative experience (i.e., complaint cause), complaint actions allow for “expressions of dissatisfaction, whether subjectively experienced or not, for the purpose of venting emotions or achieving ... goals” (Kowalski 1996, p. 179). Customers generally engage in such complaint actions when their dissatisfaction with a complaint cause such as a service or product underperformance exceeds their individual tolerance level (Ateke and Kalu 2016; Brige 2006). The complaint cause and complaint action constitute a complaint episode, which signals relationship disruption and raises customers' likelihood of switching providers. Accordingly, we hypothesize:

H₁: Customer complaints negatively affect customer retention.

Mediating Mechanisms

Perceptions of equity

Equity theory suggests that people seek balanced exchanges, with equivalent inputs and outcomes for the parties to the exchange (Greenberg 1993; Messman, Canary, and Hause 2000). As Monnickendam, Savaya, and Waysman (2004, p. 42) note, “in every exchange relationship, individuals are concerned about the inputs, outputs, and the fairness of the exchange.” Customers often consider both absolute equity (relative to the firm) and social equity (relative to comparable

others). If they perceive such equity, they tend to express more satisfaction, including satisfaction with the recovery (Piaralal, Piaralal, and Bhatti 2014), react differently to conflicts (Ohbuchi, Suzuki, and Hayashi 2001), and remain with the firm. In line with the recognition that “Customers complain because they want to be treated fairly by the company” (Siu et al. 2013, p. 675), we argue that complainers believe they have made greater sacrifices in their relationship with the firm (i.e., input) than they have received from it (i.e., output), thereby reducing their absolute equity perception. They might also believe that a comparable other with similar investments has received more output from the relationship, further reducing their social equity perception. As a result of these violations of their equity expectations, they develop more negative objective and subjective evaluations of the firm, which ultimately might lead them to switch.

H₂: Customer complaints negatively affect customer retention by decreasing complainers' perceptions of equity.

Perceptions of trust

As we noted previously, trust has been defined in many ways, but for the purposes of this research, we assert that trust reflects customers' willingness to rely on the firm, based on a belief that the firm's actions will lead to favorable rather than self-interested outcomes (Andaleeb 1996; Gambetta 1988). If customers perceive that a firm is reliable, competent, and not acting opportunistically, they likely develop stronger perceived trust. These perceptions in turn should increase retention likelihood (Gounaris 2005; Leninkumar 2017; Ranaweera and Prabhu 2003). However, failures that lead to complaints may undermine trust perceptions, because they signal that the firm is not reliable or supportive or that it prioritizes its own interests over customers'.

H3: Customer complaints reduce retention by decreasing complainers' perceptions of trust in the firm.

Moderator: Customer Investments

Customer relationship investments involve any resources—time, effort, money—that they allocate to the relationship with the firm. We predict they also function as moderators of the predicted relationships of customer complaints with customer retention.

Investments and equity perceptions

According to equity theory (Messman et al. 2000), customers who invest heavily in a relationship, such as by opening more accounts, making repeated purchases, diversifying their investments, or paying membership fees, expect commensurate returns. Due to a complaint episode, customers might develop beliefs that their returns are insufficient, and thus declining equity perceptions, as their investments rise. In an absolute sense, customers compare their own investments with the firm's; that is, a customer's perception of absolute equity reflects the ratio between the firm's investments in the relationship and their own investments. A greater perceived difference in this ratio lowers perceptions of absolute equity. Furthermore, social or comparative equity reflects whether customers believe they receive treatment from the firm that acknowledges their investments, by going beyond a standard value proposition, such as by providing recognition, elevated status, enhanced products and services (Ferguson et al. 2020; Morrisson and Huppertz 2010), price discounts (Wieseke, Alavi, and Habel 2014), or exclusive promotions (Barone and Roy 2010). This evaluation is based on customers' perceptions of what other customers receive, along with their consumption knowledge that firms tend to offer more preferential treatment to customers who invest more in the relationship. Relationship partners feel dissatisfied if they believe a similar other is receiving a better deal (Lo, Lynch, and Staelin

2007). When complaining customers invest more in the relationship, they form higher expectations, which makes it more likely that they may be dissatisfied with the ratio of what they receive, relative to what similar others receive (i.e., the social equity perception).

Investments and trust perceptions

Customers who invest more in a relationship develop stronger relational bonds with the firm, which tend to buffer the erosion of trust following a negative experience. Research on relationship quality demonstrates that accumulated positive interactions build a reservoir of goodwill that attenuates the damage caused by isolated failures (Hess, Ganesan, and Klein 2003; Garbarino and Johnson 1999). Highly invested customers draw on this reservoir when evaluating a complaint episode, applying a wider latitude of acceptance before revising their trust in the firm's reliability and benevolence. When facing a complaint, this accumulated relational assurance likely limits the diagnostic value of the episode for the firm's underlying character, thereby attenuating the erosion of trust. Accordingly, higher levels of customer investment should attenuate the negative effect of complaints on trust perceptions.

Predicting a U-shaped effect of complaint on retention

We predict that the net effect of customer complaint on customer retention depends on the strength of both trust and equity mechanisms, as well as the moderating influence of customers' relationship investments. In detail, equity and trust both should shift with relationship investments, but according to structurally different evaluative logics, such that the effects of these shifts should diverge. Equity is comparative and expectation-based, and accordingly, when customers invest more, they recalibrate their beliefs about what they deserve from the relationship. Any given failure represents a greater perceived inequity as they invest more. Trust instead reflects customers' accumulated beliefs about the firm's reliability and benevolence, such

that it develops gradually through repeated, positive interactions and should be immune to single, negative episodes. Therefore, greater relationship investments should simultaneously heighten equity-based sensitivity to failures and strengthen trust-based tolerance of them, but not proportionally or synchronously. Due to this predicted asymmetry, we do not expect equity loss and trust buffering to offset each other uniformly across investment levels. Instead, we propose a nonmonotonic (U-shaped) retention response, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of the Combined U-Shaped Effect of Investments on Retention

In more detail, as customers shift from low to medium investment levels, their equity perceptions should start relatively high but then decrease, whereas their trust perceptions start low and then increase. These customers might evaluate their relationship mainly in relation to their equity perceptions; the rise in trust levels probably is not enough to offset the drop in equity perceptions that results from their growing investments. We theorize that trust perceptions become the dominant mechanism only after customers have made substantial, higher investments in the relationship. As Figure 1 shows, in the transactional region, moving from low to medium

investments, we predict that the effect of equity on retention dominates the effect of trust. Moving from medium to high investments, as occurs in the relational region, allows trust to gain more strength and become the dominant mechanism. These two countervailing forces create a U-shaped relationship. In between these regions, we also predict a switching region, filled with moderate investment customers, who experience violations of their equity expectations and have not developed enough trust to offset this negative effect, such that they are the ones most likely to churn. Formally,

H4: The moderating effects of customer investments on the relationship between complaints and retention (a) follow a curvilinear U-shaped pattern, such that they (b) strengthen the negative effect of complaint on equity perceptions and (c) suppress the negative effect of complaint on trust perceptions.

The combination of these hypotheses underlies the framework depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

Study 1 Analytical Model

We build a game theoretic model of how complaints affect retention and how this relationship varies with customers' relationship investments. Analogous to equity and trust perceptions, we identify two analytical mechanisms that drive retention and are moderated by complainers' investments. In the model, customers differ in the extent to which they are aligned with their chosen firm, such that customers with stronger alignment derive greater utility from the relationship and are more likely to deepen their relationship investments. In this sense, the model captures relationship investments through heterogeneity in customer–firm alignment, which serves as a parsimonious representation of relationship embeddedness or investment intensity. In addition, the model does not rely on assumptions about bounded rationality, emotional reactions, or behavioral biases. We provide robustness checks in Appendix B.

Model Setup

The model consists of two firms and a set of customers. Those customers are uniformly spread across a Hotelling line represented by the $[0, 1]$ interval; the two firms appear at the endpoints, such that firm A is located at $x_A = 0$, and firm B is located at $x_B = 1$. Each firm offers a price to all customers, and customers pay as they use the good. (In Appendix B, we relax this assumption and affirm that the results are robust even if customers who switch pay the full price charged by both firms.) The Hotelling distance between a consumer and each firm reflects the mismatch between the consumer's ideal product and the firm's offering, such that we account for heterogeneous consumer tastes. The mismatch disutility, or travelling cost, for a customer located at x and firm i equals $t|x_i - x|$, where t corresponds to the unit misfit cost, capturing the disutility a customer incurs per unit of distance from their ideal product. We use V to denote consumers' reservation price for their ideal product, with the assumption that V is sufficiently large to ensure full market coverage (i.e., no customers refrain from buying). To account for the

detrimental impact of complaints, we assume that after customers choose a firm and form a relationship, a complaint episode occurs with probability γ .

Following this complaint event, complaining customers of firm i face a choice between staying with firm i and incurring the complaint cost $Cost_i^c$, or else switching to firm j and incurring the switching cost $Cost_i^s$. For example, if a customer experiences recurring billing errors, staying with their previously chosen telecommunications provider may require them to contact customer service repeatedly, contest the incorrect charges, and endure the stress and frustration associated with unresolved problems or reduced service quality during the resolution period. These burdens collectively constitute the complaint cost, which could be avoided by switching. However, switching induces its own emotional, financial, and procedural costs—separate from the travelling cost, which arises from a misfit between customers' taste and firm offerings—and those costs accrue even if the different firms' products are functionally identical (Klemperer 1995).

Customer proximity to the focal firm on the Hotelling line captures preference alignment with that firm. Specifically, for customers of firm A, lower values of x indicate greater proximity to firm A, whereas for customers of firm B, lower values of $1-x$ indicate greater proximity to firm B. Customers whose preferences are more closely aligned with their chosen firm derive greater utility from the relationship and therefore are more likely to increase their investments in the relationship over time. In this sense, proximity to the focal firm serves as a parsimonious proxy for relationship embeddedness or investment intensity, because stronger preference alignment naturally gives rise to deeper relationship investments, allowing the model to capture how heterogeneity in relationship investments shapes post-complaint retention incentives.

We allow both complaint and switching costs to be quadratic in x , such that complainers with stronger relationship investments (i.e., customers located closer to the focal firm on the Hotelling line) incur higher costs. This quadratic specification is consistent with prior research suggesting that a quadratic form can preserve an equilibrium that might not exist if the disutility function were linear in x (d'Aspremont, Gabszewicz, and Thisse 1979; Liu and Tyagi 2011). Formally then,

$$Cost_i^c = c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2, \text{ and}$$

$$Cost_i^s = s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2.$$

No Complaint Scenario ($\gamma = 0$)

We first investigate a baseline case with no complaint (see Figure 3). The utility a customer located at x gains from choosing firm i is $U_i^{nc}(x) = V - P_i - t|x - x_i|$. As Lemma 1 establishes, customers with stronger preferences for firm i choose it, and both firms charge a price equal to the unit misfit cost t .

Figure 3. Timeline of the Analytical Model (Study 1: No Complaint Scenario)

Lemma 1: In equilibrium, with no complaints ($\gamma = 0$), customers located at $x \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$ ($x \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$) choose firm A (B). The equilibrium prices are $P_A^* = P_B^* = t$.

For the proof of Lemma 1, see Appendix A.

Complaint Scenario ($\gamma > 0$)

Alternatively, after choosing a firm, there is some probability γ that a complaint event happens. Therefore, customers who previously chose firm i must undertake another choice, between staying with firm i and incurring the complaint cost or switching to firm j and incurring

the switching cost (see Figure 4).¹ If they switch from firm i to firm j , they also must pay a travelling cost, due to the greater misfit between their taste and firm j 's offerings. With U_i^c and U_i^s , we represent the utilities of staying with firm i or switching to firm j , respectively. Then with $\Delta U_i = U_i^c - U_i^s$, we can denote the additional (if any) utility that a complainer obtains from staying loyal to firm i and not switching to firm j ², as follows:

$$U_i^c(x) = V - P_i - t|x - x_i| - Cost_i^c(x), \text{ and}$$

$$U_i^s(x) = V - P_j - t|x - x_j| - Cost_i^s(x).$$

Figure 4. Timeline of the Analytical Model (Study 1: Complaint Scenario)

Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
Firms set prices simultaneously.	Customers choose one of the firms.	Firm i 's customers complain with probability γ .	Complainers decide whether to switch or not.

In turn, with probability $(1 - \gamma)$, no failure happens, and customers located at x obtain U_i^{nc} , so their expected utility, obtained from firm i , is:

$$U_i(x) = (1 - \gamma) U_i^{nc}(x) + \gamma \left(U_i^c(x) \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{U_i^c(x) > U_i^s(x)\}} + U_i^s(x) \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\{U_i^s(x) > U_i^c(x)\}} \right).$$

Lemma 2 shows that a parameter space exists, such that only customers located at $x_{m_1,i}^c < x < x_{m_2,i}^c$ switch to firm j , and therefore, $U_i^s(x) > U_i^c(x)$ when $x_{m_1,i}^c < x < x_{m_2,i}^c$. Note that $x_{m_1,i}^c$ and $x_{m_2,i}^c$ represent marginal complaining customers of firm i , who are indifferent between

¹ For parsimony, we assume that complaints happen early and that there is no contractual switching penalty, such that the price the switching complainer pays to firm i is negligible. In Appendix B, we confirm that the results are robust to the assumption that the game starts at time $t = 0$, ends at $t = 1$, and the complaint and switching decisions happen at $t_c < 1$. In this case, $U_i^c(x)$ remains unchanged, but $U_i^s(x) = V - t_c P_i - (1 - t_c) P_j - t(t_c |x - x_i| + (1 - t_c) |x - x_j|) - Cost_i^s(x)$.

² When a complaint happens, unavoidable costs might arise, regardless of whether complainers stay or switch. With unavoidable cost $Cost_i^u$, we can capture such unavoidable procedural, financial, or psychological disutility, due to the event and the hassles of complaining. However, because complainers incur $Cost_i^u$ whether they stay or switch, it should not affect their decision at this stage (i.e., $\Delta U_i(x)$).

switching to firm j or staying with firm i. With x_m^{nc} , we denote the customer indifferent between choosing firms A or B when no complaint happens.

Lemma 2: When complaints happen with probability γ , an equilibrium exists in which customers with medium investments, located at $x \in (x_{m_1,i}^{c*}, x_{m_2,i}^{c*})$, switch to firm j.

For the proof of Lemma 2, see Appendix A.

Thus, firm i's profit consists of three components: profit from its own noncomplainers, losses due to switching complainers, and profit earned from acquiring firm j's switching complainers. We summarize the expected profit of firm i as follows:

$$\pi_i = P_i[(1 - \gamma) |x_i - x_m^{nc}| + \gamma(|x_i - x_m^{nc}| - (x_{m_2,i}^c - x_{m_1,i}^c)) + \gamma(x_{m_2,j}^c - x_{m_1,j}^c)].$$

The equilibrium outcomes are in Table 1.

Table 1. Interior Equilibrium When Customers Complain with Probability γ (Study 1)
Conditions $s_1 + 2t - c_1 > 0$ and $s_0 + t - c_0 > 0$ and

$$s_1 + 2t - c_1 + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2} < c_2 - s_2 < \frac{(s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}{4(s_0 + t - c_0)}$$

Outcome	Equilibrium Value
x_m^{nc*}	$\frac{1}{2}$
$x_{m_1,A}^c$	$\frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_2,A}^c$	$\frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_1,B}^c$	$1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_2,B}^c$	$1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$P_A^* = P_B^*$	$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{t} + \frac{8\gamma}{\sqrt{(s_1 - c_1)^2 + 4(c_0 - s_0)(c_2 - s_2) + 4t(s_1 + s_2 - c_1 - c_2) + 4t^2}}}}$

$$\pi_A^* = \pi_B^*$$

$$\frac{2}{t} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(s_0 + t - c_0) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}$$

Mechanisms

In Figure 5, two mechanisms drive complaint-based churn, both part of $\Delta U_i(x)$, such that if $\Delta U_i(x) > 0$, it implies the customer stays with the focal firm, whereas if $\Delta U_i(x) < 0$, the customer switches. We map these equations to the theorized equity and trust mechanisms, with the rationale that a complaint imposes complaint costs that are analogous to diminished equity perceptions, and transition costs reflect damaged trust perceptions. Imagine a customer experiencing poor online banking performance (e.g., frequent outages, transaction processing delays). If the customer switches, these complaint-related costs disappear; if they stay, ongoing performance problems impose continuing complaint costs, which are greater for customers who have invested more in their relationship with the bank (e.g., by having multiple accounts, conducting frequent transactions), and who thus rely more on the platform. These high-investment complainers also face higher transition costs if they choose to switch banks, because it would require migrating multiple accounts, reestablishing payment routines, learning a new interface, and—in line with a trust-based mechanism—rebuilding trust in an alternative provider. Thus, greater investments amplify the equity-related cost of staying (complaint cost) and simultaneously increase trust-related reluctance to leave (transition cost). The resulting U-shaped retention effect emerges from the interaction of these countervailing mechanisms (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The Impact of Investments on Complainers' Retention (Study 1)

Notes: $c_0 = \frac{11}{20}, s_0 = \frac{35}{64}, c_1 = \frac{1}{20}, s_1 = \frac{9}{20}, c_2 = \frac{7}{4}, s_2 = \frac{3}{4}, t = \frac{1}{20}, \gamma = \frac{1}{100}$.

If we designate x as an indicator of firm A's favorability to the customer, customers who appear closer to firm A on the Hotelling line (x close to 0) prefer it more and therefore likely invest more in this relationship. Accordingly, x is informative of customer relationship investments, such that its smaller values reflect greater investments. Customers of firm A who invest more (near $x_A = 0$) also develop higher expectations; when those expectations remain unmet, they suffer more costs to stay with firm A. Thus, their complaint cost decreases quadratically with x , consistent with the equity mechanism. These customers also face a

transition cost if they switch to firm B, due to both the greater mismatch between complainers' tastes and firm B's offerings (i.e., additional travel cost $t(1 - 2x)$) and the actual switching costs (financial, psychological, procedural) associated with terminating their initial relationship and starting a new one. The transition cost reflects the trust mechanism, because at low values of x (i.e., high investments), leaving is more difficult, in terms of both the taste mismatch (travel cost) and switching costs, such that customers are more reluctant to abandon a trusted relationship and switch to another firm. On the basis of this reasoning, we propose:

Proposition 1: Without loss of generality, the net utility differential of a complainer with respect to firm A is:

$$\Delta U_A(x) = U_A^c(x) - U_A^s(x) = \underbrace{(-c_0 + c_1x + c_2x^2)}_{\text{Mechanism 1 (Complaint)}} + \underbrace{t(1 - 2x) + (s_0 - s_1x - s_2x^2)}_{\text{Mechanism 2 (Transition)}}$$

where the first term reflects the complaint mechanism, and the latter term represents the transition mechanism, which simultaneously drive customer retention outcomes.

Experimental Study 2

Goal, Context, and Method

To verify the predictions of a negative effect of customer complaints on retention (H₁), mediating roles of equity and trust perceptions (H₂ and H₃), and a moderating role of complainers' relationship investments (H₄), we undertake two randomized experiments designed to examine different regions of the proposed framework. Specifically, Study 2a focuses on lower-to-moderate investment relationships that are more characteristic of transactional exchange settings, whereas Study 2b focuses on moderate-to-high investment relationships that

are more characteristic of relational settings. Together, the two experiments are designed to capture shifts in the dominant retention mechanism, from equity in more transactional settings (i.e., Study 2a) to trust in more relational settings (i.e., Study 2b). To test the main effect, we manipulate the complaint versus control conditions, according to whether the customer incurs unwanted service fees. We also manipulate investment levels by varying the set of bank accounts held by the customer. Study 2a, which deals with the transactional region, thus is a 2 (investments: low vs. medium) \times 2 (complaint: complainer vs. control) between-subjects design. Study 2b prioritizes customers in the relational region, using a 2 (investments: medium vs. high) \times 2 (complaint: complainer vs. control) between-subjects design. The study participants, recruited from MTurk, received payment upon completing the survey. We excluded spurious data, according to the criteria outlined in Appendix C, and this exclusion rate does not vary significantly across conditions. Thus, we retained a sample of 643 participants for Study 2a (56% women) and a sample of 414 participants for Study 2b (57% women).

Procedure

Both Studies 2a and 2b rely on a quasi-experimental approach. Each study requests that participants provide the name of a U.S. bank of which they had been a customer for at least the past six months. Anyone without a U.S. bank account did not qualify to take the survey and were dismissed. In each study, we gathered data on customers' loyalty ("Would you consider yourself a loyal customer of [bank name]?" 1 = "definitely not," 5 = "definitely yes"), tenure ("How many years have you been a [bank name] customer?"), usage rate ("In the last 6 months, on average in each month, how many transactions have you made using all of your [bank name] bank accounts (e.g., checking, savings, credit or loan payments, etc.)? Transactions refer to

online or in-store purchases, wire transfers, bill pays, automated payments, loan payments, etc.”;³ five-item scale) and complaint history (“Have you ever complained to [bank name]?” 0 = “no,” 1 = “yes”).

In the second part of each study, we randomly assigned participants to the experimental conditions. After seeing the relationship investment and complaint manipulations, participants provided responses regarding their satisfaction; they also completed attention checks. Finally, they answered items designed to capture their perceptions of the bank and continued usage intentions (i.e., retention), along with attention and suspicious checks and demographic items.

Customer relationship investment manipulation

To manipulate customer relationship investments, we provided participants with descriptions of different account holdings, which we label their account composition. This investment proxy captures the extent to which customers have broader, more integrated interactions with the bank, involving multiple financial needs. In detail, participants randomly assigned to the low investment condition were prompted to imagine they maintain one savings account with the bank; those in the medium investments conditions read that they had a savings account, as well as a checking account that comes with a debit card; and participants in the high investments condition imagined that they maintained a savings account, a checking account with a debit card, a mortgage, and a credit card account. Although account composition also could correlate with switching frictions, we use it to manipulate perceived relationship embeddedness, or a sense that “more of my financial life is organized around this bank.”

Complaint manipulation

³ In financial services, customers with higher usage rates likely make more transactions, so we use average monthly transactions as a proxy for usage rate.

We randomly assigned participants to either a scenario in which a complaint event has happened or one without any complaint. We expect participants to have general knowledge about service fees and therefore use these fees as a cause for complaint. Participants in the complaint condition read a scenario that prompted them to imagine they noticed their bank had added a \$25 fee and did not know why. They call customer service and demand a refund, but the representative refuses, after which they stop complaining and end the call. This design helps rule out any potential confounding effect of firms' retention efforts, because it indicates that the firm made no such effort, and the complainer receives no refund. Participants in the control conditions instead had to imagine they called the customer service line of their bank to ask questions about which bank fees might apply to them, and the representative answered their questions, leading them to thank the representative and end the call. In this case, there is no indication that they have incurred any service fees.

Measures

To gather participants' understanding of their investments, equity perceptions, trust perceptions, and retention likelihood, we asked them: "I have made big investments into my relationship with [bank name]," "Considering the investments I have made into my relationship with [bank name], [bank name] is treating me unfairly," "Considering the investments I have made into my relationship with [bank name], I feel that [bank name] is trustworthy," and "I am going to end my relationship with [bank name] and will move to another bank" (all on 100-item scales, where 0 = "extremely disagree" and 100 = "extremely agree"). We purposefully reverse the equity scale, to encourage participants to think carefully about whether they have been treated "unfairly," such that we measure perceptions of inequity, then convert them into equity perceptions (i.e., equity perceptions = 100 – inequity perceptions). Similarly, to encourage the

participants to think carefully about whether they want to change their patronage, we frame the retention question according to intentions to end the relationship, then reverse the scale (100 – churn intentions). Finally, we use concise measures of equity and trust perceptions, rather than fine-grained multidimensional scales, for parsimony and in accordance with our research objective: To test the directional dominance and relative influence of equity versus trust in driving post-complaint retention across investment levels, concise measures are sufficient (Rossiter 2002).

Results and Discussion

Manipulation checks

To check whether the complaint manipulation was successful, we asked participants to rate their satisfaction with the bank's service ("Picturing yourself in the circumstances of the previous question, to what extent are you satisfied with [bank name]'s service?" 0 = "extremely dissatisfied," 6 = "extremely satisfied"). Customer satisfaction offers a relevant construct for checking the complaint manipulation, in line with evidence that dissatisfied customers are more likely to complain (Landon 1977; Prakash 1991). In both studies, participants in complaint conditions ($M_{2a} = 1.35$; $M_{2b} = 1.22$) indicated significantly less satisfaction than those in control conditions ($M_{2a} = 5.14$, $p_{2a} < .001$; $M_{2b} = 5.25$, $p_{2b} < .001$), indicating the success of the complaint manipulation. Also as expected, Study 2a participants assigned to the low investment condition reported significantly lower investment perceptions ($M = 46.01$, $SD = 28.05$) than participants in the medium investments condition ($M = 63.23$, $SD = 25.47$; $p < .001$). Similarly, for Study 2b, the difference in investment perceptions in the medium ($M = 62.56$, $SD = 23.46$) versus high ($M = 72.95$, $SD = 23.74$) investment conditions was significant ($p < .001$).

Analyses of variance

According to analyses of variance (ANOVA), participants in both studies indicated significantly lower retention intentions when they had been assigned to the complaint conditions ($M_{2a} = 50.76, SD_{2a} = 35.37; M_{2b} = 59.09, SD_{2b} = 33.34$) rather than the control conditions ($M_{2a} = 74.84, SD_{2a} = 31.73, F_{2a} = 82.51, p_{2a} < .001; M_{2b} = 79.23, SD_{2b} = 25.62, F_{2b} = 47.44, p_{2b} < .001$), in support of H₁. For each study, we also conduct between-subjects ANOVAs, with the complaint and investment conditions as two independent factors; retention likelihood as the dependent variable; and customer loyalty, usage rate, tenure, and complaining history as control variables. These analyses reveal a significant main effect of the complaint condition ($F_{2a} = 23.10, p_{2a} < .001; F_{2b} = 9.31, p_{2b} = .002$), a significant main effect of investments ($F_{2a} = 6.60, p_{2a} = .010; F_{2b} = 33.53, p_{2b} < .001$), and a significant interaction effect between them ($F_{2a} = 6.19, p_{2a} = .013; F_{2b} = 8.71, p_{2b} = .003$) on retention likelihood, as Figure 6 shows.

Figure 6. Study 2 ANOVA Results

Moderated mediation analysis

The moderated mediation analyses for each study rely on PROCESS model 7 (Hayes 2017) and 5,000 bootstrapped samples. In this model, investments moderate the “a path”

between the complaint condition, as the independent variable, and the mediators (equity and trust), and retention likelihood provides the dependent variable. In Study 2a, the results indicate significant moderated mediation outcomes for both equity (index = -5.24, SD = 2.38, 95% confidence interval [CI] [-10.08, -.73]) and trust (index = 1.26, SD = .74, 95% CI [.13, 3.13]), in support of H_{4a} and H_{4b}. The comparison of equity ($\beta = .52, p < .001$)⁴ and trust ($\beta = .15, p < .001$) reveals a greater effect of equity, in support of our conjecture that, in the transactional region, equity perceptions are the dominant mechanism driving retention. Because the direct effect of complaint on retention likelihood is insignificant (effect = -1.89, $p = .491$), it appears that equity and trust perceptions fully mediate the main effect.

In Study 2b, the moderated mediation effect of equity (index = -.98, SD = 1.70, 95% CI [-4.16, 2.54]) is insignificant, whereas that of trust is significant (index = 4.11, SD = 2.04, 95% CI [.50, 8.54]). Thus, at medium to high levels of investments, we find a significant moderating effect of trust perceptions, in support of H_{4b}, but not of equity perceptions, in contrast with H_{4a}. Equity perceptions appear to flatten out in the relational region. Even with greater investments, equity perceptions do not drop much in the relational region. Still, the Study 2b results affirm that trust ($\beta = .39, p < .001$) exerts a greater effect on retention likelihood than equity ($\beta = .30, p < .001$), in support of our prediction that, in the relational region, trust is the predominant driver. The direct effect of complaint on retention likelihood again is insignificant (effect = -1.32, $p = .674$), such that equity and trust fully mediate the main effect.

Notably, a one standard deviation increase in relationship investments, relative to the mean level achieved in the switching region in Study 2b increases retention intentions by 3.7%. We provide further details about Study 2 in Appendix C.

⁴ The β values reflect unstandardized regression coefficients from the PROCESS outcome model (Hayes 2017).

Conclusion

To contribute to ongoing efforts to help firms achieve effective customer complaint management, the current research proposes a conceptual framework in which complaining customers' relationship investments determine their retention, according to a U-shaped, equity–trust retention pattern, whose influences shift with the level of customer investment.

Theoretical Implications

This research is grounded in a transactional–relational exchange continuum (e.g., Agustin and Singh 2005; Macneil 1982), which predicts that customer–firm relationships range from discrete, short-term transactions to enduring, trust-based partnerships. By applying such a continuum to complaint management, we offer novel insights into how customers' evaluative focus shifts when they adopt more transactional versus more relational orientations. Along this continuum, equity functions as a dominant evaluative logic in the transactional region, whereas trust becomes the dominant evaluative logic in the relational region. In this sense, we identify equity and trust perceptions as theoretically critical for understanding complaint outcomes. In a complaint scenario, customers' equity and trust perceptions decrease, but in addition, customers' relationship investments moderate both mechanisms, in opposite directions. Greater investments heighten equity expectations, amplifying perceived inequity after a complaint. They simultaneously deepen relational attachment, buffering the deterioration in trust. This dual process reveals why the overall relationship between relationship investments and retention follows a U-shaped pattern, and why customers who make moderate investments are most likely to churn.

Thus, increasing relationship investments does not offer a uniformly protective buffer. Because they simultaneously increase vulnerability (through heightened equity expectations) and resilience (through trust buffering), nonmonotonic retention responses are a theoretically natural outcome. This reasoning also reframes moderate investment levels as a distinct decision region, not merely a midpoint on a scale. We predict that this logic also generalizes beyond complaint episodes to other moments when customers reassess their firm relationships, such as during acquisition onboarding, cross-sell/upsell attempts, after fee increases, or in response to changes in policies or terms. At these moments, firms often assume that greater investment will monotonically increase customers' receptivity or tolerance. Our framework instead predicts an intermediate switching region, in which customers are more likely to leave the firm because their equity expectations have risen faster than their sense of trust. Broadly, this equity–trust trade-off suggests that scholars might expect curvilinear responses in any situation in which an antecedent simultaneously intensifies one evaluative standard while buffering another.

Managerial Implications

The proposed framework encourages firms to shift their complaint management focus, from measuring how invested customers are, to how customers are likely to evaluate their relationship after a complaint. They might assign customers to investment-based relationship regions—transactional, switching, or relational—in which the drivers of retention vary. Customers who make low relationship investments occupy the transactional region, and retaining them depends primarily on restoring their perceived equity. Customers who have invested heavily enter the relational region, where long-term trust acts as a key stabilizing force. The switching region is critical though, because the diminished equity perceptions of these moderate investors have not been offset by greater trust, leaving them at the greatest risk of churn. By

using observable indicators of relationship investment, firms can anticipate which complainers are most at risk of churn and which mechanism is likely to sway their post-complaint decision to switch or stay. Once they have established the region in which the customer resides, managers can anticipate their post-complaint outcomes and allocate their limited recovery resources to customers more effectively. To ensure their ability to identify each customer's position on this regional spectrum, as well as monitor movements across it over time, we recommend that firms develop reliable customer investment intensity metrics and define thresholds for low, medium, and high investments in their industry context.

For managers, confused by mixed prior findings about the effectiveness of compensation as a recovery strategy, our findings help clarify that customers rely on different evaluative mechanisms, depending on their relationship investment levels. Therefore, they should expect the impact of compensation to vary, depending on whether equity or trust is the dominant driver of customers' post-complaint retention. When equity is salient, compensation restores perceptions of equity and is likely to increase retention. When trust concerns dominate, compensation does not address the main driver of the customer's decision, so it likely exerts weaker effects. In the middle, or switching region, compensation might matter, but managers should be prepared for variable, uncertain effectiveness, because these customers' reactions are shaped by both mechanisms.

The switching region is especially critical for other reasons too. Customers in this region are valuable, in terms of their prior engagement and moderate investments, so firms might consider it appropriate to deploy trust-oriented recovery strategies (e.g., apologies, reassurance, generic loyalty messaging). In so doing, they might underinvest in transactional remedies such as tangible compensation, because they assume these customers are already sufficiently committed.

Our framework cautions against such assumptions, because customers in the switching region occupy an intermediate evaluative state. Both equity-restoring and trust-oriented remedies might influence their retention, but neither is reliably sufficient on its own. To avoid misallocating their recovery resources, by emphasizing one pathway exclusively, firms should explicitly recognize that customers who invest moderately in the relationship and enter the switching region require a balanced restoration approach. For example, if one of these customers experiences a billing error and complains, a bank should respond with an apology, assurances of future reliability, and customer support, to help rebuild trust perceptions, but it also should consider proactively offering credit to reestablish equity.

In detail, we propose actionable guidelines for firms, on the basis of the equity–trust retention trade-off, for customers who occupy distinct decision regimes. These region-specific strategies reflect the influence of customers’ relationship investments on the dominance of equity concerns or trust erosion over post-complaint retention decisions.

- Transactional region (low investments): Prioritize rapid equity restoration by offering a clear explanation, tangible make-good efforts, and transparency. Recognize that customers are still heavily evaluating whether they have been treated fairly.
- Switching region (moderate investments): Recognize the highest risk of churn. Use a dual recovery strategy, including both equity restoration (e.g., refund, credit) and trust repair (e.g., sincere apology, credible assurance). Avoid prioritizing one strategy exclusively.
- Relational region (high investments): Emphasize trust repair by taking accountability, offering reassurance, and sending relationship continuity signals. Avoid relying solely on pure compensation, which may feel transactional and fail to address trust concerns.

Consistent with this segmentation logic, Study 2b indicates that different relationship investments are associated with meaningful differences in retention outcomes. This finding highlights the practical importance of aligning recovery strategies with customers' relationship investments and resultant relationship regions.

In summary, this research established a focused, theoretical foundation for understanding complaint-driven churn, on the basis of considerations of customers' equity and trust perceptions and relationship investments. By showing how these forces combine to produce a U-shaped effect on customer retention, this framework clarifies when equity or trust dominates customers' decision-making and offers scholars and practitioners a clearer means to diagnose, predict, and manage post-complaint retention.

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Appendix A. Proofs

Proof of Lemma 1

Using backward induction, in the second stage, we can find the marginal customer by solving for $U_A^{nc} = U_B^{nc}$. This solution leads to $x_m^{nc} = \frac{P_B - P_A + t}{2t}$. In the first stage, firms set prices to maximize their profit, $\pi_i = P_i(|x_i - x_m^{nc}|) = P_i\left(\frac{P_j - P_i + t}{2t}\right)$. Solving for $\frac{\partial \pi_i}{\partial P_i} = 0$ leads to $P_A^* = P_B^* = t$ and $x_m^{nc*} = \frac{1}{2}$.

Proof of Lemma 2

We use backward induction in both scenarios.

No Complaint Scenario: We solve $U_A^{nc} = U_B^{nc}$ to find the marginal customer(s), if any, and find $x_m^{nc} = \frac{P_B - P_A + t}{2t}$.

Complaint Scenario: We solve for $\Delta U_i = 0$ to find the marginal customer(s), if any:

$$\Delta U_i(x) = U_i^c(x) - U_i^s(x)$$

$$= -(c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2) + (s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2) + t(1 - 2|x - x_i|) + (P_j - P_i). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Using basic algebra, we can determine that $\Delta U_i(x) < 0$ when $x \in (x_{m_1,i}^{c*}, x_{m_2,i}^{c*})$. Any

identification of model parameters, such that $0 < x_{m_1,A}^c < x_{m_2,A}^c < x_m^{nc}$ ($x_m^{nc} < x_{m_1,B}^c < x_{m_2,B}^c <$

1), leads to an interior equilibrium, where customers located at $x \in (x_{m_1,A}^c, x_{m_2,A}^c)$ ($x \in$

$(x_{m_1,B}^c, x_{m_2,B}^c)$) switch.

$$x_{m_1,A}^c = \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 - P_A + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_2,A}^c = \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 - P_A + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_1,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 - P_B + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_2,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t - c_1 - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 - P_B + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

In the first stage, firms set prices that maximize their profit:

$$\pi_i = P_i \left[(1 - \gamma) |x_m^{nc} - x_i| + \gamma \left(|x_m^{nc} - x_i| - (x_{m_2,i}^c - x_{m_1,i}^c) \right) + \gamma (x_{m_2,j}^c - x_{m_1,j}^c) \right].$$

Substituting $x_{m_1,A}^c$, $x_{m_2,A}^c$, $x_{m_1,B}^c$ and $x_{m_2,B}^c$ with π_A and π_B and maximizing the profit functions with respect to prices leads to the equilibrium in Table 1.

Appendix B. Robustness Checks, Study 1

Timing

In the main model, we assume that complaints happen early, and the price and traveling costs that a switching complainer pays to the focal firm are negligible. If we relax this assumption, we consider a game that starts at time $t = 0$ and ends at time $t = 1$, such that the complaint event and switching decisions happen at time $t_c < 1$. In this case:

$$U_i^c(x) = V - P_i - t|x - x_i| - Cost_i^c(x)$$

$$U_i^s(x) = V - t_c P_i - (1 - t_c) P_j - t(t_c |x - x_i| + (1 - t_c) |x - x_j|) - Cost_i^s(x)$$

$$\Delta U_i(x) = U_i^c(x) - U_i^s(x) = -(c_0 - c_1 |x - x_i| - c_2 |x - x_i|^2)$$

$$+(s_0 - s_1 |x - x_i| - s_2 |x - x_i|^2) + (1 - t_c)(t |x - x_j| - t |x - x_i| + (P_j - P_i)).$$

We use backward induction and start with a case with no complaint ($\gamma = 0$). Setting $U_A^{nc} = U_B^{nc}$ and solving for a customer indifferent between firms A and B leads to $x_m^{nc} = \frac{P_B - P_A + t}{2t}$. Next, we

solve for $\Delta U_i = 0$ to find customer(s), if any, who are indifferent between staying with firm i and

switching to firm j. We find:

$$x_{m_1,A}^c = \frac{s_1 + 2t(1-t_c) - c_1 - \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1 - 2t(1-t_c))^2 + 4(c_2 - s_2)(c_0 - s_0 + (P_a - P_b - t)(1-t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_2,A}^c = \frac{s_1 + 2t(1-t_c) - c_1 + \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1 - 2t(1-t_c))^2 + 4(c_2 - s_2)(c_0 - s_0 + (P_a - P_b - t)(1-t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_1,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t(1-t_c) - c_1 + \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1 - 2t(1-t_c))^2 + 4(c_2 - s_2)(c_0 - s_0 + (P_b - P_a - t)(1-t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_2,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 + 2t(1-t_c) - c_1 - \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1 - 2t(1-t_c))^2 + 4(c_2 - s_2)(c_0 - s_0 + (P_b - P_a - t)(1-t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}.$$

In the second stage, firms maximize their expected profit:

$$\pi_A = P_A (x_m^{nc} + \gamma(1-t_c)((x_{m_2,B}^c - x_{m_1,B}^c) - (x_{m_2,A}^c - x_{m_1,A}^c)))$$

$$\pi_B = P_B ((1 - x_m^{nc}) + \gamma(1-t_c)((x_{m_2,A}^c - x_{m_1,A}^c) - (x_{m_2,B}^c - x_{m_1,B}^c))).$$

Substituting $x_m^{nc}, x_{m_1,A}^c, x_{m_2,A}^c, x_{m_1,B}^c, x_{m_2,B}^c$ into the profit functions and maximizing with respect to prices leads to the interior equilibrium in Table B.1.

Pay structure

In the main model, we assumed customers pay as they use the firm's offering; when we relax this assumption, we confirm that the results are robust if switching complainers pay the full price to both firms. For firm i's complainers, $U_i^c(x)$ remains unchanged, but $U_i^s(x)$ changes to:

$$U_i^s(x) = V - P_i - P_j - t|x - x_j| - (s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2).$$

We solve for $\Delta U_i = 0$ to find the customer(s), if any, who are indifferent between staying with firm i and switching to firm j.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta U_i(x) &= U_i^c(x) - U_i^s(x) \\ &= (V - P_i - t|x - x_i| - (c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2)) \\ &\quad - (V - P_i - P_j - t|x - x_j| - (s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2)) \\ &= -(c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$+(s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2) + t(1 - 2|x - x_i|) + P_j. \text{ (B.9)}$$

Then we solve for marginal customers (if any) and derive profit functions:

$$x_{m_1,A}^c = \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_2,A}^c = \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_1,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t + \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$x_{m_B,B}^c = 1 - \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t - \sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$$

$$\pi_A = P_A \left(\frac{P_B - P_A + t}{2t} - \gamma \frac{\sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{(c_2 - s_2)} \right. \\ \left. + \gamma \frac{\sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{(c_2 - s_2)} \right)$$

$$\pi_B = P_B \left(\frac{P_A - P_B + t}{2t} + \gamma \frac{\sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_B + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{(c_2 - s_2)} \right. \\ \left. - \gamma \frac{\sqrt{4(s_2 - c_2)(-c_0 + P_A + s_0 + t) + (s_1 + 2t - c_1)^2}}{(c_2 - s_2)} \right).$$

Although there is no closed-form solution for P_i^* , using basic algebra, we determine that $P_i^* < t$.

Table B.1. Interior Equilibrium When at $t = t_c$ Customers Complain with Probability γ .

Conditions	$s_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) - c_1 > 0$ $s_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) - c_1 + \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))} < c_2 - s_2$ $\text{and } (c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c)) > 0$
Outcome	Equilibrium Value
x_m^{nc*}	$\frac{1}{2}$

$x_{m_1,A}^c$	$\frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) - \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_2,A}^c$	$\frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) + \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_1,B}^c$	$1 - \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) + \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$x_{m_2,B}^c$	$1 - \frac{s_1 - c_1 + 2t(1 - t_c) - \sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}{2(c_2 - s_2)}$
$P_A^* = P_B^*$	$\frac{1}{\frac{1}{t} + \frac{8\gamma(1 - t_c)^2}{\sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}}$
$\pi_A^* = \pi_B^*$	$\frac{1}{\frac{2}{t} + \frac{16\gamma t(1 - t_c)^2}{\sqrt{(c_1 - s_1)^2 + 4(s_0 - c_0)(s_2 - c_2) + 4t(1 - t_c)(-c_1 - c_2 + s_1 + s_2 + t(1 - t_c))}}}$

It suffices to show that analytical conditions exist, such that $\Delta U_i(x)$ is concave in x , and solving for $\Delta U_A(x) = 0$ and $\Delta U_B(x) = 0$ uncovers four marginal customers located on the Hotelling line (i.e., $0 < x_{m_1,A}^c < x_{m_2,A}^c < x_m^{nc} < x_{m_1,B}^c < x_{m_2,B}^c < 1$). Given that $0 < P_i^* < t$, we can denote by strict lower and upper bounds of $\Delta U_i(x)$, corresponding to $P_j = 0$ and $P_j = t$ respectively, the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta U_i^L(x) = & -(c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2) + (s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2) \\ & + t(1 - 2|x - x_i|) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta U_i^U(x) = & -(c_0 - c_1|x - x_i| - c_2|x - x_i|^2) + (s_0 - s_1|x - x_i| - s_2|x - x_i|^2) \\ & + t(1 - 2|x - x_i|) + t \end{aligned}$$

For any parameter space in which $\Delta U_i^L(x)$ and $\Delta U_i^U(x)$ are concave in x , solving $\Delta U_i^L(x) = 0$ and $\Delta U_i^U(x) = 0$ results in four marginal customers located on the Hotelling line. Our main findings remain robust.

Appendix C. Study 2 Details

Manipulations

The independent variable in the conceptual model (complaint) consists of two elements (complaint cause, followed by the complaint action by the customer), so we must manipulate both elements. Incurring \$25 service fees is the cause; participants calling customer service to complain is the action. To rule out potential moderating (confounding) effects of firm retention strategies, we design this manipulation to indicate that the firm refuses the complainer's request. Therefore, the effect captured (if any) cannot be due to the firm's response but rather must stem from the joint effect of the two elements (complaint cause + complaint action) of the independent variable. Disentangling the causal effect of the complaint cause from the complaint action is beyond the scope of this article. We present the two scenarios here:

Complaint condition

You call [bank name] customer service to complain about some fees you have been charged.

You tell the representative that [bank name] has charged you a total of \$25 service fees and you do not understand why. After explaining your situation, you strongly ask for a refund.

The representative checks their system. Then, tells you they are sorry, however they cannot refund you.

You stop complaining and end the call.

Control condition

"You call [bank name] customer service to ask questions about [bank name]'s service fee rules.

You tell the representative that you know that [bank name] charges fees but are not fully familiar with the service fee rules. You want to know the fees which might affect you. The representative checks their system. Then, answers the questions, and gives you the information you need.

You thank the representative and end the call.”

Exclusion Criteria

If any of the following applies to a participant, we removed them from the sample:

- Failing to complete all survey questions or failing to pass one or more attention checks.
- Providing unrelated or inaccurate responses (e.g., copy and pastes, irrelevant response).

Descriptive Statistics for Noncomplainers (Control Condition)

Table C.1. Descriptive Statistics for Control Conditions, Study 2

	Study 2a		Study 2b	
	Investments			
	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Equity	77.5	76.1	73.3	74.5
Trust	73.9	74.8	75.6	80.4
Investments	48.0	63.0	63.5	73.9
Retention Intention	73.2	76.5	76.2	82.2

The retention rates indicated by noncomplainers in the low ($M_{2a} = 73.2$) versus medium ($M_{2a} = 76.5$) investment conditions of Study 2a do not differ significantly ($p = .363$). Similarly, in Study 2b, noncomplainer retention does not differ significantly across medium ($M_{2b} = 76.2$) and high ($M_{2b} = 82.2$) investment conditions ($p = .093$). Thus, we confirm that the U-shaped effect does not arise in the control condition.

Web Appendix

This Web Appendix reports on a study conducted to determine if the U-shaped relationship between relationship investments and post-complaint retention observed in our analytical and experimental studies manifests in a naturally occurring field setting. For this purpose, we use proprietary, customer-level data from a large financial services firm. Because observational approaches inevitably feature unmeasured differences across customers and complaint episodes, this analysis functions to assess external validity and replicate the identified patterns in our previous studies. Unobserved heterogeneity typically makes nonlinear patterns harder to detect, such that for any observed investment region, the customers within it differ in their (unobserved) relationship strength, needs, and baseline propensity to stay. Averaging across these differences tends to pull outcomes toward the middle and smooth the curvature. In addition, omitted factors plausibly correlate with investments (e.g., overall relationship quality, product needs), which would naturally shift retention in a broadly monotonic way across investment levels, changing the level or slope rather than creating an interior minimum. If we observe a U-shaped pattern in a field setting, despite these smoothing forces, it can provide supportive evidence for the generality of the proposed relationship.

Data and Sample

We obtained a proprietary data set from a leading global financial services company, established and based in the United States but with offices in several countries. It provides consumer banking, corporate and investment banking, and treasury management products and services. Although this mega-bank boasts significant market share, available competitors support customer switching and limit its monopoly power. The data consist of monthly observations

from January 2014 to June 2017, involving a sample of bank customers who complained during the study period. To avoid potentially confounding effects of multiple complaints and ensure that the customers in this sample do not have a complaint history, we focus on customers who have been with the bank for at least six months and complained only once. We remove any complainers for whom we could not specify retention outcomes,⁵ customers with more than six accounts,⁶ and complainers for whom the resolution period extended more than 10 days.⁷

Variables

Retention

Terminating a relationship can be time consuming, because it requires closing or transferring accounts. Customers with more relationship investments require even more time to close all their accounts. To alleviate concerns regarding heterogeneity in the time required to churn, as well as a potential direct influence of complainers' relationship investments on required time, we assess whether complainers are retained at the end of the fourth month after the complaint month. All the complaints in our sample were resolved within 10 days, so each complainer has more than 3.5 months to make a switching decision. We assume this period is sufficient, if they intend to leave; even if this assumption does not hold, it would attenuate (flatten) rather than amplify the proposed U-shaped effect, because customers with more relationship investments typically require more time to switch.

Relationship investments

⁵ The dependent variable is retention for four months after the complaint. Complainers who have not churned yet but whose complaint occurred less than four months prior thus are excluded.

⁶ Fewer than 2.3% of complainers held more than six accounts, and the tail is long. The results also are robust to removing complainers with more than five bank accounts.

⁷ Long complaint resolution times can affect retention; the complainer likely is required to stay, to pursue the resolution and receive information about the complaint outcome. To minimize heterogeneity in the time after a complaint is resolved and our measure of the dependent variable, we dropped these data. As a robustness check, we changed the threshold to 49 days; the results are similar.

Similar to our reasoning for Study 2, we predict that customers' account composition (i.e., number and type of accounts) reflects their relationship investments. It is not empirically feasible to differentiate all types of accounts, so we simply use the number of bank accounts held in the month before the complaint month as an indicator of complainers' investments.

Control variables

We control for customer age and tenure. To account for differences among complainers who hold the same number of accounts, we also control for their usage rate with a transaction count, as well as the dollar value of their assets and loans, prior to and after their complaint. As distinct depreciating variables for each measure, we use the weighted average in the six-month period before the complaint month or the period after the complaint, using a depreciation rate of $r = .8$.⁸ The complaint resolution period (i.e., days before the complaint is resolved) offers a measure of complaint severity; we expect complaints that take longer to resolve are more complicated and severe. Table WA.1 summarizes the descriptive statistics for the 25,068 complainers in our data set, and Table WA.2 provides the variable descriptions.

Table WA.1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	SD
Retention	0.80	1	0.40
Count of accounts	2.77	3	1.50
Customer age (year)	40.15	36.80	15.59
Customer tenure (year)	1.34	1.23	0.62
Total transactions before (dep r)	28.65	18.60	33.08
Total transactions after (dep r)	25.23	10.50	32.60
Total loan balance before (dep r)	\$53,245.80	\$61.90	\$123,903.60
Total loan balance after (dep r)	\$47,866.01	\$0	\$119,172.80
Total asset balance before (dep r)	\$3,365.52	\$110.72	\$113,183.17

⁸ To test the robustness of our results to the choice of r , we estimated the model for a range of discount factors (i.e., .6, .65, .7, .75, .85, .9, .95, .98) and obtained similar results.

Total asset balance after (dep r)	\$3,330.51	\$38.60	\$115,805.50
Complaint severity	1.68	0	2.70

Notes: dep r indicates depreciated at a rate of $r = .8$.

Table WA.2. Variable Descriptions

Variable	Description
Retention	Indicates whether the complainer is retained at the end of the fourth month after the complaint month
Count of account	Number of bank accounts one month before the complaint month
Customer age	Customer age (in years) before the month of the complaint
Customer tenure	Customer tenure (in years) before the month of the complaint
Total transactions before (dep r)	Weighted average of all transactions (ATM, in person, checks, direct deposit, bill pay, debit card, online, phone, mobile, or other transactions) the customer has made in the period of six months before the complaint month
Total transactions after (dep r)	Weighted average of all transactions the complainer has made on or after the complaint month. This variable spans from the complaint month to when the complainer churns or four months after complaint (whichever comes first)
Total loan balance before (dep r)	Weighted average of total loan balance in \$ amount across all loan accounts (e.g., credit card balance, student loan, personal loan, etc.) in the period of six months before the complaint month
Total loan balance after (dep r)	Weighted average of total loan balance in \$ amount across all loan accounts; this variable spans from the complaint month to when the complainer churns or four months after complaint (whichever comes first)
Total asset balance before (dep r)	Weighted average of total asset balance in \$ amount across all asset accounts (e.g., savings, checking, certificate of deposit, investments, etc.) in the period of six months before the complaint month
Total asset balance after (dep r)	Weighted average of total asset balance in \$ amount across all asset accounts; this variable spans from the complaint month to when the complainer churns or four months after complaint (whichever comes first)
Complaint severity	Number of days between complaint open date and close date; how long it has taken for the bank to resolve the complaint

Model-Free Evidence

Figure WA.1 shows the U-shaped effect of the count measure of the number of accounts on retention. Complainers with two and three accounts show the lowest retention rate, providing model-free evidence of the proposed U-shaped effect.

Figure WA.1. U-Shaped Effect of Investments on Retention (Model-free Evidence)

Joint Estimation with Copulas

To identify the effect of the number of accounts on retention, we must account for potential sources of endogeneity (e.g., customers self-select into complaining status, complaints happen for different reasons). Therefore, we implement joint estimation using copulas, as proposed by Park and Gupta (2012) and implemented by Gui, Meierer, and Algesheimer (2019). The copula-based approach does not require instrumental variables and provides a practical method for addressing endogeneity when valid instruments are unavailable, a common challenge in empirical research (Rossi 2014). Therefore, it is particularly well suited for our setting. The model is applicable to random coefficient logit model. For identification purposes, the endogenous regressors must be nonnormally distributed (Park and Gupta 2012), which a Shapiro–Wilk test shows to be the case.

Methodology

In a linear model, with some exogenous covariates, as well as other covariates that are potentially correlated with the structural error term, we can denote customer i 's outcome of

interest by Y_i and assume that it is a linear function of exogenous covariates X_i and endogenous covariates P_i . Then we use ξ_i for the structural error term, and α and β to indicate the model parameters, such that

$$Y_i = X_i' \beta + P_i \alpha + \xi_i$$

Park and Gupta (2012) assume that the (unobserved) marginal distribution of the structural error term is normal, and they argue that model estimates are fairly robust to misspecification of the marginal distribution of the structural error term. To obtain the marginal distribution of the endogenous regressors in the observed data, we use a nonparametric Kernel density function. According to the Sklar's theorem (Sklar 1959), given the marginal distributions of the endogenous regressor $H(p)$ and the structural error term $G(\xi)$, there exists a Copula function C that defines the joint distribution of $H(p)$ and $G(\xi)$:

$$F(p, \xi) = C(H(p), G(\xi)) = C(U_p, U_\xi),$$

where $U_p = H(p)$ and $U_\xi = G(\xi)$ are the marginal distribution functions. Park and Gupta (2012) use a Gaussian copula to estimate the joint distribution and density functions with U_p and U_ξ .

This method can extract the endogenous component of the structural error term from the exogenous component. Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_i &= \sigma_\xi \cdot \rho \cdot P_i^* + \sigma_\xi \cdot \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \cdot \omega_i \\ Y_i &= X_i' \beta + P_i \alpha + \sigma_\xi \cdot \rho \cdot P_i^* + \sigma_\xi \cdot \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \cdot \omega_i \end{aligned}$$

Adding P_i^* as a regressor leaves ω_i uncorrelated with all the other regressors. Thus, the model can be estimated to obtain the unbiased model parameters.

Result

We find a U-shaped effect of the number of accounts on retention, as detailed in Table WA.3.

Table WA.3. Results

Variable	Coefficient	SE
Constant	73.80**	2.10
<i>Customer Investments</i>		
Number of accounts	-7.54**	.93
Number of accounts (p2)	1.85**	.11
<i>Control Variables</i>		
Customer age (year)	.09**	.02
Customer tenure	.82**	.38
Total transactions before (dep r)	-.38**	.01
Total transactions after (dep r)	.57**	.01
Total asset balance before (in \$10000, dep r)	-.06	.53
Total asset balance after (in \$10000, dep r)	.07	.57
Total loan balance before (in \$10000, dep r)	-1.80**	.10
Total loan balance after (in \$10000, dep r)	2.29**	.10
Complaint severity (resolution time)	-.57**	.01
<i>Endogeneity Variables</i>		
PStar. count of accounts	-0.62	.70
PStar. count of accounts (p2)	-1.98**	.75

Notes: p2: power of two; r = .8; To ease reading, all numbers are multiplied by 100

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